

The Role Of The Victory Park In Educating Young People In The Spirit Of Patriotism

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Abstract: The article analyzes the role of the Victory Park in educating young people in the spirit of patriotism, and shows effective methods for preserving historical memory and educating young people to be loyal to the Motherland.

Keywords: youth education, patriotism, Victory Park, historical memory, spiritual education.

INTRODUCTION.

The main goal of every state is to educate the younger generation as spiritually mature individuals who value national values. In this regard, the role of places such as the Victory Parks is incomparable. Such places serve not only to impart historical knowledge, but also to instill a sense of pride and responsibility in the hearts of young people. Today, it is important not to alienate young people from their nationality in the current of globalization. Victory Parks are a unique opportunity to bring young people closer to national history and values. This article, based on personal observations and scientific sources, shows the educational significance of Victory Park.

Main part: Victory Park always makes me think more deeply about the fortitude of our ancestors. During my visit to Victory Park in Tashkent, I witnessed stories of selflessness and courage during the war years. Here, the courage of our ancestors is vividly reflected through monuments and exhibits. Such places are an invaluable place for young people not only to study history, but also to receive spiritual education. Such parks bring young people

closer to national values, and they feel like part of the nation.

Patriotic education plays an important role in the formation of young people as personal and socially mature individuals. This concept includes not only love for the Motherland, but also the preservation of historical memory and an understanding of civic duty. From a pedagogical point of view, introducing young people to national values does not limit them to acquiring knowledge, but also serves their moral development. Historical memory is a means of enriching the spirituality of young people, through which they not only learn about history, but also understand the courage and self-sacrifice of their ancestors. International experiences, such as the Moscow Victory Park in Russia or war memorials in Germany, show that such places are important in orienting young people to national pride and educational goals.

Uzbekistan's Victory Park plays an important role in youth education. Victory Park in Tashkent demonstrates advanced experience in introducing young people to history using modern pedagogical and technological tools. For example, this park uses interactive museums, 3D excursions, and virtual

spaces. These technologies increase young people's interest in history and actively involve them in the educational process. The resolution of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev "On measures to improve the spirituality of youth and educate them in the spirit of loyalty to the Motherland" specifically mentions the issue of closely connecting the younger generation with history and spirituality. This resolution emphasizes the importance of orienting young people to historical memory and national values through the use of places such as Victory Parks.

Scientific research and practical experience show that Victory Parks are an effective tool for orienting young people to historical memory and national values. The integration of these places with modern technologies will give even greater results in the education of the younger generation. Therefore, the development of the activities of the Victory Park and their widespread use in educational processes is of urgent importance.

When young people hear about the life and courage of war heroes, they feel a high sense of responsibility towards themselves. It is in these places that they understand the need to be loyal to the Motherland, love it and appreciate it. When I participated in open lessons held in the Victory Park, I saw interest and admiration in the eyes of young people. This indicates their need to learn history. In promoting national values, I think that historical places such as the Victory Park have enough potential. Excursions and events held in these places broaden the worldview of young people and form a sense of national pride in them. For young people, these exhibits allow them to see history not just from books, but live. This helps them make historical memories a part of their lives.

Since today's youth are close to technology, it is important to use interactive tools in the Victory Parks. In my opinion, virtual excursions,

multimedia exhibitions and interactive lessons are an effective way to engage young people. Digital excursions organized in the Victory Park in Tashkent increase young people's interest in the park and allow them to study history in more depth.

Conclusion: The Victory Parks are truly a place of spiritual education for young people. In these places, the younger generation learns to be proud of their nation as an integral part of history, to be inspired by the courage of their ancestors. They also form feelings of loyalty to the homeland in every way, to protect and cherish the motherland as the apple of their eye. Developing such places, organizing more educational events for young people there will be an important step in promoting national values. Therefore, attracting young people to the Victory Park and using these places in their education is one of the main tasks facing the state and society. Because young people who understand and appreciate history feel a deep sense of responsibility in building the future.

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